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Design and tolerance analysis of interstage transport and diagnostics line for the APOLLON LFA Facility

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ABSTRACT

This document describes the design of a dogleg transfer line between a plasma injector and a second plasma stage reaccelerating the plasma in the multi-GeV scale.

It follows the work described in the ARIES Deliverable D18.1 [1] and an ARIES internal report on the description of possible beam diagnostics [2].

In this document, a comprehensive study of beam diagnostics for the line is provided, together with the design of the magnets and its mechanical implementation, including beam pipe, vacuum chambers and supports. A product breakdown structure of the full line is provided.

ARIES Consortium, 2021

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Executive summary

This document describes the design of a dogleg electron transfer line between two stages, a plasma injector at an energy of 200-300 MeV and a second plasma stage reaccelerating the plasma in the multi-GeV scale.

First, we describe the input parameters and constraints used in the study, such as the input beam parameters, the expected output beam characteristics and the mechanical constraints.

We then summarize the beam studies performed to optimize the transport of the electrons along the line. These beam studies allow to fix the number of magnets together with their magnetic strength and their location. The output beam distributions and an estimate of the sensitivity to errors are provided.

A preliminary design of the electromagnets is then described, followed by a proposal of beam diagnostics which should be installed along the transfer line to measure in particular the beam charge, position, transverse and longitudinal profile, mean energy and energy spread and the emittance. This diagnostics is based on the beam characteristics and on the required precision at the possible location of the diagnostics.

The mechanical design is then described. This mechanical design is useful in particular to confirm the locations of the diagnostics when including the necessary space reservation for assembling the line (flanges, supports...). It is also useful to design the interface between the laser – plasma chambers and the transfer line.

Finally, the elements needed to build the line are summarized in a Product Breakdown Structure.

1 Introduction

A 2-stage acceleration experiment is being considered at the multi-petawatt laser facility APOLLON Long Focal Area (LFA), previously named CILEX, with transport of electrons from an all-optical injector in the non-linear (blowout) regime to a booster in the linear regime.

A theoretical study of a transfer line for an electron beam with an energy in the range 200 – 300 MeV was performed within ARIES in 2017 – 2018 and is described in [1].

In the current document, we describe an update of this study taking into account additional requirements (section 2). The theoretical study is complemented by a first real design of the transfer line, including the design of the magnets provided by the SIGMAPHI company (section 4), a study of beam diagnostics suitable to measure in particular the beam charge, position, transverse and longitudinal profile, mean energy and energy spread and the emittance (section 5), and a preliminary mechanical design (section 6).

The proposed design is still preliminary. A list of points to address in order to improve this design is thus described in the conclusion (section 8).

2 Requirements

2.1 ELECTRON BEAM CHARACTERISTICS

2.1.1 Input beam characteristics

The input beam characteristics considered in this study are the beam characteristics at the exit of the laser – plasma interaction region. They are summarized in Table 1. The reference energy was initially considered to be in the range 200-300 MeV. However, because of constraints on the field and on the position of the first dipole magnet, the beam energy allowing a good optimisation of the beam transport (described in section 3) was found to be 320 MeV.

Reference energy [MeV]	320
Charge [pC]	10
Normalized emittance [μm]	1
$\beta_{x,y}$ [mm]	1
$\alpha_{x,y}$ [no units]	0
RMS energy spread [%]	1
RMS bunch length [fs]	5
Peak current [kA]	1
Repetition rate [Hz]	< 0.02
FWHM time length	10 fs

Table 1 : Initial beam properties

2.1.2 Output beam constraints

The challenges of such a transfer line are to get a final beam size of a few micrometres and a final bunch length of a few tens of femtoseconds despite nonlinear terms brought by the transfer line, misalignment and field errors, and collective effects like space charge. The exact values of the required bunch size and length to allow a proper beam reacceleration are however not yet known. Conversely, a study of the electron reacceleration using the output distribution of the studies described in this document could be performed.

2.2 MECHANICAL INTERFACES

The transfer line is to be installed in the experimental hall of APOLLON facility between two laser – plasma interaction chambers with fixed positions shown in Figure 1. The constraints on the installation have imposed a transverse separation of 3 m between the centres of the two plasma chambers whereas the longitudinal separation is fixed at 7.675 m.

Inside the laser – plasma interaction chambers, the available space between the laser plasma interaction point and the chamber wall is 1135 mm. An existing permanent magnet dipole used for the first experiments in the APOLLON Long Focal Area (LFA) facility is foreseen to be used inside

the laser – plasma interaction chambers. The characteristics of this dipole (mechanical drawings and the magnetic field map) were used in this study. In addition, a space of 20 cm between the dipole and the exit wall of the plasma chamber was considered to allow for additional beam diagnostics inside the plasma chamber.

The height of the beam line is 1200 mm.

Figure 1: The two existing laser - plasma interaction chambers installed in the APOLLON LFA area, with a view of the foreseen transfer line.

3 Beam transport optimization

3.1 OPTIMIZATION OF THE MAGNETIC ELEMENTS

The beam transport was optimized as described in [1] in order to limit the dispersion and thus the beam size due to the initial energy distribution (achromaticity), to avoid the lengthening of the bunch due to different path lengths along the line (isochronous) and to be as independent as possible of the initial beam divergence (astigmatism). In addition, the position of the first and the last dipole magnet is constrained as mentioned in section 2.

In order to satisfy these conditions and to be able to transport the beam between the two laser – plasma interaction chambers, a symmetric dogleg type transfer line was chosen, and the type of magnets, their location and their strength determined to optimize the beam transport along the line.

The layout resulting from this optimization is shown in Figure 2 and the main magnetic requirements for the magnets listed in Table 2, for a beam pipe diameter of 30 mm.

Figure 2: Layout of the beam transfer line. The dipoles are shown in red, the quadrupoles in blue, the sextupoles in green and the slit C1 selecting the beam in energy in grey.

Dipole	Length (mm)	Field (T)	Angle (rad)	Angle (deg)	Gap (mm)
D1	277.2	1.724	0.44381689	25.4288344	18
D2	100	6.26E-02	0.00586809	0.33621693	
Quadrupole	Length (mm)	Gradient (T/m)	Bore radius (mm)		
Q1	60	221.478774	6		
Q2	60	-109.06006	6		
Q3	100	-1.13E+00	18		
Q4	100	1.59E+01	18		
Q5	100	-8.91E+00	18		
Sextupole	Length (mm)	Gradient (T/m ²)	Bore radius (mm)		Nota: By = K2 x ² /2
S1	100	4.55E+02	18		

Table 2: Magnet parameters. The fields are calculated for an energy of 320 MeV. The gradient of sextupoles is defined as the second derivative of the magnetic field with the position.

3.2 PARTICLE TRANSPORT ALONG THE LINE

The transport along this line of 100000 particles sampled from the initial beam has been performed to get some characteristics of the beam like the centroid or the rms sizes. The final beam distribution at the exit of the transfer line is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Final beam distribution in different planes with no collimators.

These distributions exhibit significant tails. In order to reduce these tails to measure the beam core, we added a collimator (with an inner diameter of 8 mm) in front of Q1 and a vertical slit with width $= \pm 3.66$ mm (corresponding to a cut in energy of $\pm 1\%$) before Q3.

The final distributions with the collimator and the slit is shown in Figure 4. The use of the collimator and of the slit reduces the beam charge by 40%.

Figure 4: Final beam distribution in different planes with the collimator and the slit.

3.3 SENSITIVITY OF THE LINE TO ERRORS

The final beam characteristics can be affected by errors such as a different initial beam (position or angle) or magnet misalignments or field errors. The sensitivity to such errors was studied in ref [1].

The conclusions of these studies on the initial beam errors are that:

- the initial position error should be below 10 μm to keep the final position offset below 10 μm
- the initial angular error should be below 5 mrad to keep the final position offset below 10 μm

Errors due to the magnets can be divided into static errors (the characteristic time of variation is large compared to the beam repetition time) and dynamic errors (which vary with a period smaller than the repetition time). Static errors can be corrected for using a correction scheme, which has to be determined in the future taking into account the available diagnostics.

The studies of dynamic errors show that the line is very sensitive to errors. The transverse misalignment of the quadrupoles is the most critical: their misalignment should be stable from shot to shot in the range of a few micrometres. Secondly, tilt errors of the two permanent dipoles D1 should

stay in the range of a few tens of microradians. Finally, the field in all magnets should stay stable to 10^{-4} which, in the case of electromagnets, can be achieved with standard power supplies.

4 Preliminary design of the magnets

4.1 INTRODUCTION

The Q1, Q2 and D1 magnets have to be located close to the laser – plasma interaction point, and thus inside the laser – plasma interaction chambers. Therefore, permanent magnets are foreseen. Between the two laser – plasma interaction chambers, electromagnets will be used.

A design of these electromagnets was obtained from the SIGMAPHI company for dipole, quadrupole, and sextupole. Mechanical design, electric characteristics and CAD files are available.

The main characteristics of these magnets given by beam dynamic simulations are summarized in Table 3.

Dipole	Length (mm)	Field (T)	Angle (°)	Gap (mm)
D2	100	0.06	0.33	30
Quadrupole	Length (mm)	Gradient (T/m)		Bore radius (mm)
Q3	100	7.67		18
Q4	100	14.2		18
Q5	100	13.7		18
Sextupole	Length (mm)	Gradient (T/m²)		Bore radius (mm)
S1	100	455		18

Table 3: Main characteristics of the magnets

The location of the magnets is shown on Figure 2.

Magnet simulations have been performed with the OPERA 2020 software. The magnetic circuit, yoke and poles have been considered as XC10 steel for material properties. The BH curve is shown on Figure 5.

Figure 5: Magnetic material characteristics

4.2 DIPOLE

The dipole is a straight H shaped dipole and the main trajectory is bent with an angle of 0.34° on a radius of 6662.36 mm (Figure 6). The yoke length is 101.35 mm. The magnet circuit dimensions have been optimized for 0.15 T field at the magnet center. The field in the poles is not saturated T as shown on Figure 7.

Figure 6: Dipole geometry

Figure 7: Dipole yoke saturation at 0.15 T

The dipole coils are designed with plain copper 2x5.6 mm conductors. Each coil is made of 176 turns and the operating current is fixed to 12,5A. About 80 W is dissipated by each coil leading to a temperature increase of 27°C. The magnets are not water-cooled, but just cooled by natural air.

The magnetic parameters, dimension and weight, electrical parameters and cooling parameters are summarized in Table 4.

<p>MAGNETIC PARAMETERS</p> <p>Bending angle (°) 0.86° Gap (mm) 30 mm Nominal Field (T) 0.15 T Effective length (mm) 100 mm</p>	<p>ELECTRICAL PARAMETERS</p> <p>Operating current (A) 12.5A Magnet voltage (V) 6.1 V Magnet resistance (Ohm) 0.491 Magnet DC power (W) 76.8</p>
<p>DIMENSIONS AND WEIGHT</p> <p>Total weight (Kg) < 110 kg Yoke weight (kg) 70 kg Magnet Shape H shape Yoke length (mm) 101.35mm Numbers of bloc per yoke Solid steel Steel Solid steel XC10 Magnet total length (mm) <230 mm Magnet Total width (mm) 268x437</p>	<p>COOLING PARAMETERS</p> <p>Copper seize (mm) 2x5.6 plain Copper Copper grade CUC1 Coil Shape Race track Coil weight (Kg) 14.2 kg Numbers of turns (per pole) 176 Temperature rise (°C) 27</p>

Table 4: Dipole parameters

4.3 QUADRUPOLES

Octagonal shape is chosen for the quadrupole geometry as shown on Figure 8. The same geometry is available for both Q3, Q4 and Q5.

The magnetic characteristics and main dimensions are reported in Table 5. The current is adjusted to reach the performances. Yoke and poles are not saturated with a maximum of 1 T in the magnetic circuit localized in the poles as shown on Figure 9. Plain copper of 2x5.6 mm is used for the conductors wounded helicoidally with 72 turns per coil. The magnets are not water-cooled, just natural air cooling. Operating current for each quadrupole and electrical parameters as well as temperature rise are summarized in Table 5.

<p>MAGNETIC PARAMETERS</p> <p>Bore diameter (mm) 30 Nominal Gradient Field (T) 11.6/5.48/8.66 Effective length (mm) 100</p>	<p>DIMENSIONS AND WEIGHT</p> <p>Total weight (Kg) <50 gg Yoke length (mm) 90 mm Solid Steel XC10 Magnet total length (mm) ≤150 mm Magnet Total width (mm) 274 mm without support and alignment plate</p>
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ELECTRICAL PARAMETERS		COOLING PARAMETERS		
Operating current	16A for 11.6 T/m	Copper seize	2x5.6 plain copper	
	11.8A for 8.66 T/m		Copper Grade	CU-C1
	7.6A for 5.48 T/m		Coil shape	Racetrack
Magnet voltage	2.7V for 11.6 T/m	Numbers of turns (per pole)	72	
	1.9V for 8.66 T/m		Temperature rise	24°C for 11.6 T/m
	1.2 V for 5.48 T/m			12°C for 8.66 T/m
Magnet resistance	0.171 Ohm for 11.6 T/m		4.7°C for 5.48 T/m	
	0.164 Ohm for 8.66 T/m			
	0.159 Ohm for 5.48 T/m			
Magnet DC power	44 W for 11.6 T/m			
	23 W for 8.66 T/m			
	10 W for 5.48 T/m			

Table 5: Quadrupole parameters

Figure 8: Quadrupole geometry

Figure 9: View of the yoke saturation at the maximum current of 16 A for quadrupole Q1

4.4 SEXTUPOLE

The sextupole will be realized with a yoke assembled in 6 parts as shown on Figure 10. The magnetic characteristics and main dimensions are reported in Table 6. Plain copper 2x5.6 mm conductor will be used to realize 16 turns air-cooled coils. The operating current is 18.8 A, leading to a temperature rise of about 15°C. For a gradient of 225 t/m², there is no saturation of the iron as shown in Figure 11 with a maximum of 0.42 T in the poles.

<p>MAGNETIC</p> <p>Bore diameter (mm) 40</p> <p>Nominal Gradient Field (T/m²) 225</p> <p>Effective length (mm) 100</p>	<p>DIMENSIONS AND WEIGHT</p> <p>Total weight (Kg) < 50 kg</p> <p>Yoke Weight (Kg) 26 kg</p> <p>Yoke length 90 mm</p> <p>Steel solid steel XC10</p> <p>Magnet total length (mm) <125 mm</p> <p>Magnet Total width (mm) 246 mm without alignment and support plate</p>
<p>ELECTRICAL PARAMETERS</p> <p>Operating current (A) 18.8</p> <p>Magnet voltage (V) 1.1</p> <p>Magnet resistance (Ohm) 0.06</p> <p>Magnet DC power (KW) 22 W</p>	<p>COILS</p> <p>Copper seize (mm) 2x5.6 plain copper</p> <p>Copper Grade CU-OF</p> <p>Number of turns (per pole) 16</p> <p>Temperature rise (°C) 15.2</p>

Table 6: Sextupole parameters

Figure 10: Sextupole geometry

Figure 11: View of the yoke saturation at the maximum current of 18.8 A for sextupole H1

5 Beam diagnostics

In the frame of the ARIES project, the electron beam produced in the injection stage will be first controlled and characterized in contrast to very compact interstage transport schemes. For that, the characterization of the electron beam with destructive but also non-invasive methods is crucial. Listing all needed beam diagnostics is thus the first step towards the characterization of the electron beam and the validation of the beam transportation.

Regarding beam diagnostics and characterization, a distinction should be done between the commissioning and the operation phases. Two stages should be thus distinguished: beginning of the commissioning (with robust but less accurate measurements) and end of the commissioning or operation (with a stabilized beam and more accurate measurements). Beam diagnostics with relatively simple implementation should be firstly developed in order to make sure to have reliable and robust measurements considering the complex characteristics of the beam at APOLLON LFA (or use of already existing diagnostics in the industry such as Bergoz Integrating Current Transformers (ICTs)). More complex diagnostics could then be developed and implemented in a second step.

A detailed internal ARIES report has been published that compares and then identifies the suitable diagnostics for a full characterization of the electron beam along the transfer line [2]. This chapter summarizes the most important points described in this report.

5.1 BEAM PARAMETERS AND MEASUREMENTS

The transfer line should enable the characterisation of the electron beam both to check the characteristics of the beam produced by the laser – plasma interaction and to ensure that the beam is properly transported along the line. Measurements of several beam parameters are thus foreseen to be performed along this line:

- Charge measurement.
- Position measurement.
- Transverse profile measurement.
- Mean energy and energy spread measurement.
- Emittance measurement.
- Longitudinal profile measurement.

All these measurements will certainly be performed downstream the slits selecting the beam in energy. The features of the electron beam downstream these slits are summarized in Table 7 and are shown also in Figure 12 and Figure 13 (slits located at $s = 1.4$ m in the latter). It is very important to point out that since the repetition rate is lower than 0.02%, beam characteristics may be not reproducible from shot to shot. Single-shot measurement is thus necessary, that makes the development of diagnostics much more complex.

Energy	320 MeV
Vertical transverse size	Range [0.01 – 2] mm (see Figure 12)
Horizontal transverse size	Range [0.01 – 10] mm (see Figure 12)
Normalized transverse emittance (without dispersion contribution)	~ 2.5 μm in X plane and 7.5 μm in Y plane (see Figure 13) in the drift located in the middle of the transfer line (area where an emittance-meter should be installed)
Bunch length	6 ps from 1.4 m up to 7.5 m in Figure 13
Charge	~ 10 pC (from 40 pC up to 100 pC before beam collimation)
Peak current	~ 10 A for a charge of 10 pC and a bunch length of 1 ps
Repetition rate	< 1 shot / minute

Table 7: Beam properties along the transfer line

Figure 12: Beam size (RMS and maximum amplitude) along the transfer line. A collimator of $\Phi=8$ mm is added at the entrance of Q1 (giving a cut at ± 20 mrad). A Slit with a gap of ± 3.66 mm is added at $s = 1.4$ m (giving a cut at $\pm 1\%$ in energy).

Figure 13: Normalized emittance (left) and bunch length (right) along the transfer line. A collimator of $\Phi=8$ mm is added at the entrance of Q1 (giving a cut at ± 20 mrad). A Slit with a gap of ± 3.66 mm is added at $s=1.4$ m (giving a cut at $\pm 1\%$ in energy).

Taking into account these beam features, the suitable diagnostics will be identified in the next sections for each beam parameter to be measured.

5.2 CHOICE OF DIAGNOSTICS

Robust and single shot diagnostics should be developed for APOLLON LFA and attention must be given in the signal to noise ratio. All diagnostics will be based on imaging systems with screens, except the ones used for charge measurements and BPMs used for position measurements as a second step. Translation stages incorporating several screens are needed. The cameras used in the imaging systems should have very low noise and very high quantum efficiency in order to ensure that the signal to noise ratio and the dynamic range are sufficiently high.

The measurement of energy and of energy spread is crucial for the two-stage acceleration. The only method that can be considered for APOLLON LFA at least for the first step is the use of a dipole and of an imaging system with screen. It has been checked with simulations that the dipole D2 is strong enough for this measurement.

The only conceivable solution for emittance measurement which can be quickly usable is the “energy-scan” method [3] [4] [5] [6] (two quadrupoles, a dipole and an imaging system with screen to perform measurement in one transverse plane). It has the big advantage to use the same system as the one foreseen for energy measurement. However, a study of the resolution that can be achieved with this method should be performed. It should be also ensured that the method allows single-shot measurement. A study of a set-up allowing measurement in the two transverse planes would also be interesting. Other systems for emittance measurement, much more complex to implement, may be developed in a second step in order to gain in precision and to measure the emittance in the two transverse planes (e.g. Multiple OTR screens [7], Pepper-Pot [8]).

To ensure correct measurements of position, imaging systems with screens are essential and they can be used in the same time for transverse profile measurements. Beam Position Monitors (BPMs) could

be considered later to have online measurements in order to perform corrections of static errors, and they can be used also to measure the beam charge.

ICTs from Bergoz Company are very reliable and should be used for charge measurements. More precisely the Turbo-ICTs should be chosen in order to insure single-shot measurements and better noise immunity.

To determine the longitudinal profile, pyroelectric detectors [9] will be firstly used to measure coherent transition radiation in the far-infrared regime since this method is easy to implement and not very costly. However, the accuracy is only of around 100 fs – 1 ps and another measurement method should be thus developed to improve the accuracy. Electro-optic sampling method is a good candidate because it is not very costly, provides a resolution down to 50 fs and even less [10] [11] [12] [13] [14] [15] [16], and should work for the beam parameters of APOLLON LFA. Its development should however start early since it is not easy to implement.

Figure 14 and Table 8 summarize the diagnostics selected (at different stages of the commissioning) as well as their location and quantity for each beam parameter foreseen to be measured. Different types of diagnostics are needed all along the transfer line. In order to check that the characteristics of the beam can allow a good matching into the second interaction chamber, an imaging system together with a pyroelectric detector will be installed in the second interaction chamber in order to measure respectively the beam size (and position) and the longitudinal profile. Since the accuracy of bunch length measurement is around 100 fs – 1 ps, this kind of measurement can only prove that the bunch length is below or not this range. It will be thus needed in a second step to develop an electro-optic sampling system in order to have a resolution that can go down to 50 fs.

Figure 14: Location of the diagnostics selected for the APOLLON LFA transfer line at the different stages of the commissioning.

Beam parameters to be measured		Type of diagnostics	Number of diagnostics	Location of diagnostics
Charge		Turbo ICTs / BPMs	3	Positions 1, 2 and 3
		Possibly Faraday Cup	1	Position 3
Position	1 st step	Imaging system: Lanex, YAG, OTR	4	Positions 1, 2, 3 and 4
	2 nd step	BPMs (cavity, stripline or button)	3	Positions 1, 2 and 3
Transverse profile		Use of the same systems as for position measurement at 1 st step		
Mean Energy / energy spread		Variable dipole + large 1 inch' screens (stage)	1	Position 2

Transverse emittance	1st step	Energy-scan: use of the same system as for energy measurement (pos. 2) + 2 quadrupoles (magnets already existing in the conception of the line)		
	2nd step	Multiple OTR screens or Pepper-Pot, ... TBD	1 (cumbersome)	Position 2
Longitudinal profile	1st step	Coherent transition; Pyroelectric detector	4	In front of each imaging system (Positions 1, 2, 3 and 4)
	2nd step	Electro-Optic Sampling	1	Position 4

Table 8: Diagnostics selected for the transfer line (at different stages of the commissioning) with their location and quantity for each beam parameter foreseen to be measured.

The proposed positions of the diagnostics centre, taking into account the mechanical constraints (available space, flanges), are listed in Table 9 together with the diagnostics length (that includes their vacuum chamber). These positions are used to compute the beam distributions used in section 5.3.2.

Position from Figure 14	Diagnostic	Position along the line (m)	Length (mm)
1	Slit	1.363	150
	Imaging system	1.516	150
	BPM	1.641	100
	Turbo ICT	1.781	40
2	Imaging system	4.168	150
	BPM	4.293	100
	Turbo ICT	4.433	40
3	Imaging system	6.680	150
	BPM	6.808	100
	Turbo ICT	6.948	40
4	Imaging system	8.338	150

Table 9: Position of the diagnostics centre along the line and diagnostics length (that includes their vacuum chamber).

5.3 ZOOM ON CHARGE AND BEAM PROFILE MEASUREMENTS

5.3.1 Turbo-ICT

The turbo ICT from Bergoz company (model Turbo-ICT-CF4”1/2-34.9-40-UHV) responds to the requirements for beam charge measurements as can be seen in Table 10

[17]. They allow single-shot measurements of few pC beam charges [18] (resolution is of the order of 0.1 pC) for bunch lengths down to the nanosecond. Thanks to a wide dynamic range, they can measure bunch charges up to 300 pC.

	Requirements	Bergoz specifications of Turbo-ICT (model Turbo-ICT-CF4”1/2-34.9-40-UHV)
Minimum bunch length	~ 1ps	< 100 ps
Charge resolution	100 fC	20 fC rms or 1% of a single pulse charge ➔ 100 fC rms for a 10 pC bunch charge
Maximum charge	50 pC	300 pC
Mode	Single-shot	Single-shot

Table 10: Requirements for beam charge measurements and specifications of the Turbo ICT (model Turbo-ICT-CF4”1/2-34.9-40-UHV) from Bergoz Company.

5.3.2 Imaging screens

The imaging screens will be used to perform beam profile and position measurements in the first step of the commissioning. BPMs can be considered as a second step for online beam position measurements since they allow non-destructive measurements (see section 5.3.3).

Choice between Lanex, YAG and OTR screens will be driven by the needs in luminosity and resolution. From the one hand, Lanex screens generate the highest amount of light, followed by YAG screens and then OTR screens. From the other hand, OTR screens have the highest resolution, followed by YAG screens and then Lanex screens.

From COXINEL experiments, it has been strongly recommended to choose a camera with very low noise and very high quantum efficiency. The camera Hamamatsu ORCA-Flash4.0 V2 has thus been chosen for the following studies (noise of the camera: 1.6 electrons rms at 100 frames/second; Quantum efficiency: 82%).

Figure 15 shows the distributions simulated at the four positions foreseen for the imaging screens. Simulations start at the exit of the plasma with a Gaussian distribution and a beam charge of 10 pC. A collimator is set at the beginning of the transfer line to cut $1 \sigma = 1\%$, and the beam charge after collimation is of 6.8 pC.

Figure 15 : Distribution X-Y of the electron beam at the four positions foreseen for the imaging screens. The amplitude is given in pC/bin area with a bin area= $50.0 \times 50.0 \mu\text{m}^2$ at positions 1 and 3, of $6.5 \times 6.5 \mu\text{m}^2$ at position 2 and of $1.0 \times 1.0 \mu\text{m}^2$ at Position 4. At positions 1 and 3, the cut in the distributions is due to the slit.

5.3.2.1 Size of the imaging screens

The largest beam size is at Position 1. It is needed to have imaging screens of 1 inch (or a little bit bigger) in order to image the whole beam.

5.3.2.2 Beam optics

Since the camera Hamamatsu ORCA-Flash4.0 V2 has a sensor area of 13.3 mm^2 , it is needed to design an optical system with a magnification of 0.5 in order to perform profile imaging of the whole beam.

5.3.2.3 Charge resolution

At position 1, the charge density on the Lanex ranges from 0.1 to 1 pC per mm^2 , which is well within the linear range of several types of Lanex screens, as measured in ref [19].

The minimum beam charge density is at Position 1 since the beam is the least focused at this position. For this position, Figure 16 shows the cumulated beam charge per total beam charge as a function of the minimum beam charge per bin. The minimum beam charge density that the monitor should be able to measure is of $3.0 \cdot 10^{-1} \text{ fC}/(50 \times 50) \mu\text{m}^2$ and of $7.0 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ fC}/(50 \times 50) \mu\text{m}^2$ in order to be able to measure respectively 95% and 99.7% of the total beam charge.

Figure 16: Cumulated beam charge per total beam charge as a function of the minimum beam charge per bin at Position 1.

The yield of a Lanex screen, i.e. the number of photons created in a Lanex screen per incident electron has been calculated at 546 nm using the Lanex screen described in ref [20] to be $5 \cdot 10^3$ photons/e⁻. Measurement of the yield of a lanex Fast Back as a function of the energy gives a similar value of about $5.5 \cdot 10^3$ photons/e⁻ [21].

The yield of an OTR screen has been calculated following ref [22] for a beam energy of 300 MeV and for an optics selecting photons in the wavelength region [400 – 700] nm. The total number of photons that the detector receives is of $1.7 \cdot 10^{-2}$ photons/e⁻.

Considering a magnification of 0.5, a solid angle of $2.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$ sr for a Lanex screen, a circular aperture of photons collection of radius 0.1 rad for an OTR screen, an angle of the camera relatively to the screen of 45° for a Lanex screen, some transmission factors for the optics (e.g. interference filter at 546 nm for Lanex screen and of 550 ± 10 nm for OTR screen) and the use of the camera Hamamatsu ORCA-Flash4.0 V2, calculation results of the number of photoelectrons and of camera counts produced on one pixel of the camera for the minimum beam charge density allowing to have 95% and 99.7% of the beam charge (i.e. respectively $3.0 \cdot 10^{-1} \text{ fC}/(50 \times 50) \mu\text{m}^2$ and $7.0 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ fC}/(50 \times 50) \mu\text{m}^2$ at Position 1) is shown on Table 11 for Lanex [20] and OTR [22] screens.

Screen type	Number of photoelectrons / pixel		Number of counts / pixel	
	95% beam charge	99.7% beam charge	95% beam charge	99.7% beam charge

Lanex	9.4	2.2	1.3	$3.1 \cdot 10^{-1}$
OTR	$4.4 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$6.2 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.4 \cdot 10^{-2}$

Table 11: For Lanex and OTR screens, calculations of the number of photoelectrons and of camera counts produced on one pixel of the camera for the minimum beam charge density allowing to have 95% and 99.7% of the beam charge (i.e. respectively $3.0 \cdot 10^{-1}$ fC/(50 x 50) μm^2 and $7.0 \cdot 10^{-2}$ fC/(50 x 50) μm^2 at Position 1).

Since the noise of the camera is of 1.6 electrons rms at 100 frames/second, it is thus possible to image 95% of the beam with a Lanex screen at the most critical position (Position 1) if a camera of very low noise and high quantum efficiency is chosen.

An OTR screen cannot be used to perform beam imaging at Position 1. Table 12 show the results of the same calculations performed for an OTR screen (and a Lanex screen) at Position 4. In fact, a high spatial resolution is needed at this position, which can be achieved with an OTR screen (see section 5.3.2.4). The minimum beam charge density is much higher at Position 4 since the beam is much more focused, i.e. of $8.1 \cdot 10^{-1}$ fC/(1.0 x 1.0) μm^2 and of $5.1 \cdot 10^{-2}$ fC/(1.0 x 1.0) μm^2 to have respectively 95% and 99.7% of the beam charge (see Figure 17). Results show that the number of photoelectrons is above the camera noise level for OTR (and Lanex) screen even with 99.7% of the beam charge. An OTR screen can thus be used at Position 4 to image the beam with high resolution. It should be noticed that a YAG screen can also be used at Position 4 since this type of screen generates more light than OTR screen and its resolution might be enough (see section 5.3.2.4). A set of neutral-density filters should be mounted on a motorized filter wheel in order to adapt the intensity of incident light on the camera.

Screen type	Number of photoelectrons / pixel		Number of counts / pixel	
	95% beam charge	99.7% beam charge	95% beam charge	99.7% beam charge
Lanex	63780	3990	9110	570
OTR	2940	185	420	26

Table 12: For Lanex and OTR screens, calculations of the number of photoelectrons and of camera counts produced on one pixel of the camera for the minimum charge density allowing to have 95% and 99.7% of the beam charge at Position 4 (charge of respectively $8.1 \cdot 10^{-1}$ fC/(1.0 x 1.0) μm^2 and $5.1 \cdot 10^{-2}$ fC/(1.0 x 1.0) μm^2).

Figure 17: Cumulated beam charge per total beam charge as a function of the minimum beam charge per bin at Position 4.

5.3.2.4 Spatial resolution

The spatial resolution of Lanex screens is of the order of 50-100 μm. The one of YAG screens is of the order of 10-50 μm and can reach even less than 10 μm [23] [24] [25] [26]. An OTR screen allows usually beam size measurement with less than 5 μm of resolution [27] [28] [29] [30].

In terms of spatial resolution, Lanex screens can thus be used for the imaging screens located at Position 1 and Position 3 while YAG and OTR screens should be used at Position 2 and Position 4, see Figure 15. It has been checked in section 5.3.2.3 that the luminosity is sufficiently high at these positions to use these types of screens. However, it is recommended to have translation stages incorporating three types of screens (Lanex, YAG and OTR) for each of the four locations. In fact, beam dynamics simulations are preliminary and the simulations of the beam distribution along the transfer line shows that this distribution varies fast as a function of the longitudinal direction (beam direction).

5.3.2.5 COTR

Electron beam imaging with incoherent OTR is widely used, but imaging with coherent OTR (COTR) can be extremely tricky since the incoherent distribution becomes overwhelmed by the donut-like coherent distribution. Several techniques have been developed to mitigate the effect of coherent transition radiation (CTR) [24] [31] [32] [33] [34] [35]. For scintillating screens, a solution is to carefully choose the angle in order to direct COTR away from the camera, or to delay the camera acquisition until the prompt transition radiation disappears (use of a very fast camera shutter that can open at the nanosecond scale). For OTR screens, mitigation techniques are much more complex to implement.

At APOLLON facility, the electron bunch length should be of the order of the picosecond scale at the three first locations (Positions 1, 2 and 3) foreseen for transverse profile measurements (cf. Figure

13). COTR should thus not be emitted at these positions and incoherent OTR or fluorescence (the latter being emitted with a scintillator screen) can be thus used for such measurements.

Even though Figure 13 shows a bunch length of $1 \sigma = 12$ ps at Position 4, many particles are localized within ± 200 fs inside the pulse at this position and COTR can thus be emitted. Techniques should be thus tried to mitigate the effect of COTR at Position 4 where profile measurements with screens are foreseen.

5.3.3 Beam Position Monitors

There are essentially three types of BPMs: striplines, button BPMs and cavity BPMs. All are non-destructive and can achieve micrometre resolution in single-shot. Striplines are usually used on LINACs and Boosters, button BPMs on storage rings, and cavity BPMs on LINACs for FEL operation and / or on new generation storage rings.

The spatial resolution of BPMs becomes worse with the decrease of beam charge. It is thus important to have BPMs that can achieve the desired resolution for the beam charge at APOLLON facility that is expected to be low, around 10 pC.

In ref [36] a spatial resolution of 10 μm rms could be achieved in single-shot measurement using button BPMs for bunch charges of 15 pC, and using stripline BPMs for bunch charges of 10 pC (resolution of the order of 1 μm rms was achieved with both button and stripline BPMs for beam charges of 100 pC). In ref [4], the expected resolution of designed stripline BPMs was of 30 μm for 1 pC beam charge.

The cavity BPM is indeed the BPM that can offer, still in a very compact design, the highest spatial resolution for the lowest charges. Ref [37] shows a resolution down to a micrometre with cavity BPMs for few pC beam charge and single-shot measurement.

Button or stripline BPMs could be used for beam position measurements at Positions 1 and 3. In fact, the beam size is large at these locations and the spatial resolution of this type of BPM is largely sufficient. Cavity BPMs could be used at Position 2 since a higher resolution could be needed due to the small beam size at this location.

6 Preliminary mechanical design of the line

A preliminary mechanical design has been studied using the following input drawings:

- The drawings of the plasma interaction chamber in the APOLLON LFA (provided by LULI)
- The drawing of the D1 dipole magnet (provided by LLR)
- The drawings of the electromagnets (provided by the Sigmaphi company)
- The drawing of the TurboICT (provided by the Bergoz company)
- The drawings of the BPMs, the imaging system and the slit used on COXINEL [4] (provided by the SOLEIL synchrotron)

This preliminary mechanical design allowed positioning the elements on the line with realistic space constraints. It is shown on Figure 1.

The beam line starts inside of the interaction chamber with 2 quadrupoles and a dipole. Each element is installed on an alignment support, bolted to the base of the interaction chamber. Then a special adaptation is needed to exit the interaction chamber. This adaptation is tightened to the side panel of the interaction chamber with an EPDM gasket. This adaptation follows the angle of the line at $25,4^\circ$ then end with a CF40 flange. This allows the installation of a valve to isolate the vacuum of the interaction chamber from the vacuum of the beam line. The same principle is applied to the exit interaction chamber.

Figure 18 - View of the valve and adaptation installed on the interaction chamber

Two “girder” chassis support the transfer line joining the interaction chambers. Each element, magnet or diagnostic, supported by the girder is mounted on a dedicated alignment plate. Every equipment must have reference surfaces, compatible with the laser tracker system, to obtain the precision required.

Figure 19 shows the exit of the first chamber up to the first magnets, with the slit, the imaging system, the BPM and the TurboICT. All these elements can be implemented on the line although the space between the valve and the first magnet is only of 0.6 meter.

The slit consists in two tungsten plates which can be moved independently by stepper motors in order to change both the slit width and central position.

The imaging system is based on a motorized tree which can position on the beam axis three different screens at 45° . The tree is installed on the top of a chamber which has two viewports, one on each side, allow to image the front or the back of the screens. An additional port located below the chamber can be used by the pumping system.

Figure 19: Slit and diagnostics implemented at the exit of the first interaction chamber

7 Product Breakdown Structure

The Product Breakdown Structure (PBS) of the transfer line is shown in Figure 20. It is composed of 4 main products, Magnets, Diagnostics, Mechanics and Vacuum System. Each product is split into sub-products down to the level of objects which can be obtained from one provider. The number of identical objects is indicated between brackets.

8 Conclusion and future plans

1 - Magnets	1.1 - Dipoles	1.1.1 - Permanent magnet dipoles (2)	3 - Mechanics	3.1 - Beam pipes	
		1.1.2 - Electromagnetic dipoles (2)		3.2 - Bellows	
	1.2 - Quadrupoles	1.2.1 - Permanent magnet quadrupoles (4)		3.3 - Imaging chambers (3)	
		1.2.2 - Electromagnetic quadrupoles (6)		3.4 - Supports	
	1.3 - Sextupoles	1.3.1 - Electromagnetic sextupoles (2)		3.5 - Stepper Motors	
1.4 - Power supplies (10)					
2 - Diagnostics	2.1 - Slit (1)		4 - Vacuum system	4.1 - Pumps	
	2.2 - Turbo ICT (3)			4.2 - Gauges	
	2.3 - Beam Position Monitors (3)			4.3 - Valves	
	2.4 - Imaging Systems	2.4.1 - Lanex Screen (2)			
		2.4.2 - OTR Screens (2)			
		2.4.3 - Translators (3)			
		2.4.4 - Optical readout (4)			
		2.4.5 - Cameras (4)			

Figure 20: The Product Breakdown Structure

This document presented a study of an electron transfer line from an all-optical injector in the non-linear (blowout) regime to a booster in the linear regime.

Although the line is about 8 m long, the strong requirements on the output beam characteristics lead to constraints on the number and position of the magnets. This in turns leads to quite a restricted space between laser – plasma interaction chambers and the magnetic elements, requiring some care in the choice and positioning of the diagnostics.

The outcome of this study is however that such a line should be feasible in terms of magnetic elements, in terms of beam diagnostics to measure the main beam characteristics and in terms of mechanical interfaces.

This study is still preliminary, and several points would need to be addressed to finalize the design of the line, in particular:

- A study of the required mechanical precision, the alignment procedures and of the alignment plates
- The need for beam steerers, which would probably need to be coupled to one of the proposed magnets to save some space
- A study of the feasibility of beam emittance measurement in single-shot using the Energy scan technique, and a study of the resolution that can be achieved with this technique. Eventually, a study of a set-up with this technique allowing measurement in both X and Y planes.
- A study of suitable diagnostics for beam emittance measurement with higher accuracy than the Energy Scan technique and in both X and Y planes, such as multiple OTR screens or Pepper-Pot techniques
- A study of the electro-optic sampling technique that can allow longitudinal beam profile measurements down to 50 fs (or less) of resolution
- The vacuum system
- The command – control system

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Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
BPM	Beam Position Monitor
CAD	Computer-Aided Design
FEL	Free Electron Laser
ICT	Integrating Current Transformer
LFA	Long Focal Area
LINAC	LINear ACcelerator
OTR	Optical Transition Radiation
PBS	Product Breakdown Structure
YAG	Yttrium Aluminium Garnet